

Studies on Some N-Hydroxy-N,N'-Diarylsubstituted-*p*-Toluamidines as Metal Complexing Agents : Spectrophotometric Determination of Manganese(II)**

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A number of N-hydroxy-N,N'-diarylsubstituted-*p*-toluamidines have been synthesised and employed for the spectrophotometric determination of micro quantities of manganese. These compounds develop ethanol soluble deep-green manganese complexes (at λ_{\max} 620-635 nm with ϵ 5220-7550 l.mol⁻¹cm⁻¹) in ammonical medium. The influence of pH, time, temperature and other experimental variables on the determination have been discussed.

IN connection with our studies concerning the synthesis and analytical applications of N-hydroxy-N,N'-diarylbenzamidines,¹⁻⁷ the present paper reports the use of some newly synthesised N-hydroxy-N,N'-diaryl-substituted-*p*-toluamidines (I-VI) for the spectrophotometric determination of microgram quantities of manganese. The present work deals with the various aspects of determination of manganese of the proposed reagents.

(I) Ar=C₆H₅; Ar'=C₆H₄CH₃-*p*- (II) Ar, Ar'=C₆H₄CH₃-*p*- (III) Ar=C₆H₄CH₃-*m*-; Ar'=C₆H₄CH₃-*p*- (IV) Ar=C₆H₅; Ar'=C₆H₃(CH₃)₂-2,5-, hydrochloride (V) Ar=C₆H₄CH₃-*p*-; Ar'=C₆H₃(CH₃)₂-2,5-, hydrochloride (VI) Ar=C₆H₄CH₃-*m*-; Ar'=C₆H₃(CH₃)₂-2,5-, hydrochloride.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents: A Carl-Zeiss 'Specord' ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer with matched 1-cm quartz and silica cuvettes was employed for recording the spectra. For all absorbance measurements an ECIL UV/VIS spectrophotometer model GS-865 was employed. The pH values of the solutions were measured with a Systronic pH meter type-322.

Standard solution of manganese(II) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of MnCl₂·4H₂O in double distilled water containing a few drops of dilute hydrochloric acid (0.5 N). The manganese content of this solution was determined complexometrically*.

H-Hydroxy-N,N'-diaryl-*p*-toluamidines(I-VI) were prepared by the condensation of equimolar quantities of appropriate N-aryl-benzimidoyl chloride and N-arylhydroxylamine in ether at low temperature (0-5°), following the method of Deb and Mishra⁹. Either, the resulting hydrochloride salt was recrystallised from absolute alcohol containing a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid (B.D.H., A.R.) or the free base liberated by the action of ammonia on the crude hydroxyamidine hydrochloride was recrystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (2 : 1). All these compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

0.1% w/v solution of the reagents in ethanol (90%) were used for colour development purposes.

All the reagents used were of A. R. Grade.

Procedure for the determination of manganese: In a 25 ml volumetric flask place a suitable aliquot of solution containing requisite amount of metal. To this, add 5-10 ml of reagent solution and few drops of ammonia solution (2N) so as to adjust the pH of the solution to pH 9-0. Allow to stand for 1 hr (with occasional shaking) during which the development of the colour to full intensity is accomplished. Dilute the solution to 25 ml. with sufficient amount of alcohol and water so as to get a final 60% alcoholic concentration of the system. Measure the absorbance at λ_{\max} against alcohol as blank. Deduce the amount of manganese in the sample solution by comparing with a standard calibration curve. Fig. 1 shows the absorption spectra of manganese complexes of N-hydroxyamidines.

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Fig. 1 Absorption spectra :
 -O- 4.40 ppm Mn + N-Hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-p-tolyl-p-toluamide
 Δ-4.40 ppm Mn + N-Hydroxy-N, N'-di-p-tolyl-p-toluamide.
 □-4.40 ppm Mn + N-Hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2,5-dimethyl) phenyl-p-toluamide hydrochloride.
 ●-4.40 ppm Mn + N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-(2,5-dimethyl) phenyl-p-toluamide hydrochloride.
 ▼-3.04 ppm Mn + N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-p-tolyl-p-toluamide.
 ■-1.81 ppm Mn + N-Hydroxy-N-tolyl-N'-(2,5-dimethyl) phenyl-p-toluamide hydrochloride.
 O-O.1% W/V N-Hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-p-tolyl-p-toluamide in ethanol.

Results and Discussion

Effect of time and temperature : When few drops of any of the hydroxyamide in ethanol were added to manganese(II) solution and the pH increased with a drop of ammonia solution, a deep green colouration developed immediately. However, the maximum intensities of the complexes were obtained only after standing for 1 hr. The colour of the manganese complexes was stable for atleast 40 hr. and was insensitive to variation of temperature in the range 20-35°.

Effect of pH and amount of reagent : When reagent solution was mixed with manganese solution at pH 7.0, a brown suspension soluble in ethanol was observed. However, mixing of the reactants at pH 7.5 adjusted with ammonia resulted into the development of a green colour. The development of the colour to full intensity required a pH value of

8.5-10.0. Moreover, the complex were found to be less stable at pH above 10.0. Below pH 8.5 the process of colour development was very slow and lower absorbance values of the complexes were obtained. The use of a 1 : 10 molar ratio of the metal to reagent was found to be necessary for complete colour development. However, to ensure maximum development of colour 1 : 15 molar ratio of manganese to ligand was always employed. A large excess of the reagents (30 : 1 reagent to metal) was found to have no adverse effect on the determination of manganese.

Molar absorptivities, sensitivities, precision and optimal concentration : The molar absorptivities of the complexes vary in the range 5220-7550 l.mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹, whereas the wavelengths of maximum absorption are found in the region 620-635 nm. Beer's law is followed by the systems upto 10 ppm. of Mn. Ringbom plot^{10,11} suggests an optimum and effective concentration range of 1.6-10.0 ppm of manganese. Sandell sensitivities¹² of the complexes are in the range 0.0072-0.0105 μg cm⁻² of Mn. The relative standard deviation of the methods (calculated from 10 samples each containing 100 μg Mn/25 ml) lies in the range ±0.60 to ± 0.90%.

The metal to ligand stoichiometry of the manganese complexes could not be determined by any of the conventional methods.

Interferences : In the determination of 4.0 μg/ml of manganese at pH 9.0±0.2, the following ions did interfere to the extents (μg/ml) given in parenthesis : F⁻(50), Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, CH₃COO⁻, SCN⁻, S₂O₃²⁻, B₄O₇²⁻, NH₄⁺ or alkali metals (1000); Be²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ba²⁺ or Sr²⁺ (100); citrate, Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, or UO₂²⁺ (100); AsO₄³⁻ (50); PO₄³⁻ (80); selenate or tellurate (400); Tl³⁺ or Th⁴⁺; MoO₄²⁻ (20). However, oxalate, EDTA, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Pd²⁺ and Fe³⁺ seriously interfere with the determinations.

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